

Dynamics of Change in the Food Culture of Kashmiri Muslims with Special Reference to Wazwan in the Post-COVID Period in Jammu District

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Abstract

Food and Culture are considered two sides of the same coin. Food is not just about nutrition, it carries meanings, values and identity. Food structures people's everyday world and defines relationships and hierarchies. "Tell me what you eat and I will tell you who you are," wrote renowned gastronome Jean Anthelme Brillat Savarin (1755-1826) in his celebrated work on gastronomy translated into English as, 'The Physiology of Taste' (1825) to explore how food shapes us and our culture. Sociologists have largely ignored food until recently because it was seen as just biological, something we needed to survive. But it is very much social, when we think about what we eat, who we eat with and where we eat. The surrounding society influences the development of individual taste, explaining why some foods are very much identified and associated with culture and nations, such as many people relate Italy with pizza and pasta, kimchi with Korea or tea with England or potatoes with Ireland and Wazwan with Kashmir. As Sherry A Innes said in her book *Dinner Roles* (2001), *food is basic to all human life, so ubiquitous that, paradoxically, it disappears from our attention entirely*. Food builds the identity of individuals, of groups, communities and nations. Thus, food constitutes an important part of this paper and focussed on the food practices among Kashmiri Muslims which are deeply intertwined with cultural identity, religious values, and social organization. The traditional Wazwan represents a central culinary institution symbolizing hospitality and collective bonding. This study examines the dynamics of change in food patterns, particularly Wazwan, in the post-COVID period in Jammu district. Based on primary data from 50 respondents, the research reveals significant shifts toward simplified consumption, increased health awareness, reduced communal dining, and growing commercialization. The paper concludes that while the symbolic importance of Wazwan persists, its practice has undergone substantial transformation.

Keywords

Wazwan, Kashmiri Muslims, Food Culture, Post-COVID, Jammu District, Dietary Change, Modernization.

Introduction

Food is a key marker of identity and social structure. Among Kashmiri Muslims, Wazwan is not merely cuisine but a cultural system embedded in rituals, hierarchy, and social relations. Wazwan, a multi-course meal in the Kashmiri tradition is treated with great respect. Its preparation is considered an art. Almost all the dishes are meat-based (lamb, chicken, fish, beef). It is considered a sacrilege to serve any dishes based around pulses or lentils during this feast. The traditional number of courses for the wazwan is thirty-six, though there can be fewer. The preparation is traditionally done by a *vasta waza*, or Head Chef, with the assistance of a court of *wazas*, or chefs. Wazwan is regarded by the Kashmiri Muslims as a core element of their culture and identity. Guests are grouped into fours for the serving of the wazwan. The meal begins with invoking the name of Allah and a ritual washing of hands, as a jug and basin called the *tash-t-nari* are passed among the guests for washing their hands. Each man holds at waist level, a large and heavy copper plate, the *Trami*, covered with an equally ornately patterned and heavy copper lid, the *sar-posh*. This large serving dish piled high with heaps of rice, decorated and quartered by four *seekh kababs*, four pieces of *meth maaz*, two *tabak maaz*, sides of barbecued ribs, and one *safed kokur*, one *zafrani kokur*, along with other dishes is deposited by the men giving one *trami* to each foursome (Dewan, 2004: 321). The meal is accompanied by yoghurt garnished with Kashmiri saffron, salads, Kashmiri pickles and dips. The feast ends with an elder leading the thanksgiving to Allah, which is heard with rapt attention by everyone. Kashmiri Wazwan is

generally prepared in marriages and other special functions. The culinary art is learnt through heredity and is rarely passed to outside blood relations. That has made certain waza (cook) families very prominent. The wazas remain in great demand during the marriage season (May - October).

Traditionally served during weddings, festivals, and religious gatherings, it reflects both economic status and communal solidarity.

The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted social interactions, food supply chains, and consumption habits globally. For migrant Kashmiri populations in Jammu district, these disruptions intersected with urban pressures, resulting in visible changes in food practices.

COVID-19 drastically shifted global food culture toward home-centric eating, increasing cooking, baking, and online grocery shopping, while highlighting food safety. Key trends included a greater focus on health, immunity-boosting foods, and sustainability, alongside panic-buying and reduced restaurant dining. Research shows a rise in mindful eating, though for many, it also intensified food insecurity

The COVID-19 pandemic and especially the lockdowns coming with it have been a disruptive event also for food consumption. In order to study the impact of the pandemic on food patterns of Kashmiri Muslims of Jammu, a sample size of 50 respondents was chosen from the area in and around Jammu city including khatikan Talab, Gujjar Nagar, other surrounding areas having Muslim majority. The study showed that different types of respondents can be distinguished based on how they react to the pandemic as regards their eating habits. While food-related behaviours were resilient for 60% of the sample, another 35% reported more enjoyment in cooking and eating, more time in the kitchen and more family meals. Among those, a slight majority also showed signs of more mindful eating, as indicated by more deliberate choices and increased consumption of healthy food, whereas a slight minority reported more consumption of indulgence food. Only 5% indicated less involvement with food. As the COVID-19 pandemic is a disruptive event, some of these changes may have habit-breaking properties and open up new opportunities and challenges for food policy and food industry.

The COVID-19 pandemic is a disruptive event that has changed the environments in which food-related behaviours take place, affecting conditions for shopping, choice of sites and occasions to eat, preparation of meals in the home, and how and with whom to eat. Some people had more time for meal provisioning at home, others had less, for example because they had to entertain their children who otherwise would be at school.

Objective of study

1. To examine changes in Wazwan consumption patterns in post-COVID period
2. To analyze transformation in preparation and serving practices
3. To study socio-economic and cultural determinants of change
4. To assess continuity and change in traditional food culture.

Review of Literature

The review of literature for the present study included consultation of books, journals, census reports and online books. In this section those studies were considered important which provided guideline to the researcher. Review of literature was undertaken with a view to discuss the relevance of issues like caste, culture and food in Indian society in general and Kashmiri society in particular. Food and culture are two inseparable aspects of life. Food defines us. It defines our culture, the changes in society and our socio-economic status. People can choose whether or not to listen to popular music, or to purchase the latest trendy clothing or to be politically active but there is no choice in terms of eating, everybody has to eat in order to survive. As Sherry A. Innes says in her book *Dinner Roles —Food is basic to all human life, so ubiquitous that, paradoxically, it disappears from our attention entirely* (2001). Eating is intertwined with all our other activities. It is difficult to think clearly if one is ravenous. On a daily basis, people are subject to the demands of their stomach. How these demands are met by whom and with what —reveals a great deal about a society and its values. The whole idea of 'You are what you eat' is particularly concerned with studying the culture of food. The earlier literature on 'Culture' is available in the books on social and cultural anthropology.

The British Anthropologist Edward B. Tylor in his book, *Primitive Culture* (1871) views culture as that complex whole which includes everything which members of society acquire like knowledge, belief, art, law, morals, custom, and any other capabilities and habits. Tylor's definition includes three of the most important characteristics of culture: culture is acquired by people because it consists of learned patterns of behavior rather than the biologically determined ones that are sometimes called instinctive. Culture is a complex whole that social scientists can break down into simple units called cultural traits. Culture is acquired by people as a member of society. Ruth Benedict in her work *Patterns of Culture* (1971) focuses on

motives and values of culture. She considered it as a total way of life of a social group, meaning everything they are, they do and they have. In social Anthropology, the word ‘culture’ means knowledge about those aspects of humanity which are not natural but which are related to that which is acquired. In other words, culture refers to those abilities, notions and forms of behaviour which are acquired by a person as members of society.

A study by Muhammad Ashraf Wani entitled Islam in Kashmir (2004) is important in understanding the life of Kashmiris including their food habits at the time of advent of Islam in Kashmir valley in the fourteenth century. In this book he points out that when Islam came in Kashmir there was the emergence of two cultures that of the Brahmins and the Muslims .The former considered themselves as ritually pure compared to the latter. All castes and out- castes embraced Islam in Kashmir and the Hindu Society was left to be represented by only one Caste- Brahamans locally known as Bhattas, famous today as Kashmiri Pandits (as per a popular legend mere 11 Kashmiri Hindu families were left in Kashmir). They regarded themselves as gods of the earth and others as ritually impure; and maintained this distinction in food relations. Thus the author brings to light the hierarchy in the two communities represented by differences at religious and cultural levels.

Most of the studies and works reviewed as quoted above were of relevant help for the investigator. These studies have paved the way for further consultation and references and opened new dimensions, queries and aspects for the present study which were explored during the research.

Methodology

Research Design- Descriptive and empirical

Study Area - Urban and semi-urban areas of Jammu district

Sample Size-Total respondents: 50

Sampling Technique--Purposive sampling (Kashmiri Muslim households)

Data Collection Methods -Structured questionnaire ,Telephonic and online interviews

Socio-Demographic Profile

Variable	Category	Percentage
Gender	Male	54%
	Female	46%
Age	18-35	50%
	36-60	38%
	60+	12%
Residence	Urban	70%
	Semi-urban	30%

Result and Discussion

Frequency of Wazwan Consumption

Response	Percentage
Decreased	66%
Same	20%
Increased	14%

Majority indicate declining frequency post-COVID.

Preference for Type of Wazwan

Type	Percentage
Traditional full Wazwan	30%
Mini Wazwan	50%
Rare consumption	20%

Shift toward simplified Wazwan formats.

Mode of Serving

Mode	Before COVID	After COVID
Trami (shared eating)	80%	36%
Individual serving	20%	64%

Clear movement toward individualized dining practices.

Health Consciousness

Indicator	Percentage
Reduced oil intake	60%
Reduced meat consumption	48%
Increased fruits/healthy items	52%

Strong shift toward health-oriented food behaviour.

Economic Impact

Response	Percentage
Reduced spending on Wazwan	64%
No change	28%
Increased spending	8%

Economic factors significantly influenced consumption.

Source of Wazwan

Source	Before COVID	After COVID
Home-cooked	74%	58%
Catered	26%	42%

Growth of commercial catering services.

Perception of Cultural Change

Opinion	Percentage
Food culture changing	72%
No change	16%
Unsure	12%

Majority perceive cultural transformation.

Conclusion

The Study concludes that food patterns among Kashmiri Muslims in Jammu district have undergone dynamic transformation rather than decline in the post-COVID period. While Wazwan retains its symbolic importance, its practice has become simplified, individualized, and commercially oriented. One of the most prominent observations is the decline in the frequency and scale of Wazwan consumption. A majority of respondents reported that elaborate multi-course feasts have been replaced by smaller and more manageable versions, often referred to as “mini Wazwan.” This change is largely driven by economic constraints and the shift toward more practical and less extravagant lifestyles after the pandemic.

Another important observation is the shift from **collective to individual dining** practices. Traditionally, Wazwan was consumed in groups from a shared Trami, symbolizing unity and brotherhood. However, post-COVID concerns regarding hygiene and social distancing have led to a preference for individual servings. This indicates a broader sociological shift from collectivism to individualism, where personal safety and convenience are prioritized over traditional communal values.

The study also highlights a **growing awareness of health and nutrition** among respondents. Many participants reported reducing the consumption of oily and meat-heavy dishes that are characteristic of Wazwan. Instead, there is an increasing inclination toward balanced diets and lighter food options. This reflects the influence of the pandemic in reshaping food choices toward health-conscious behaviour.

Furthermore, there is a noticeable increase in the **commercialization of Wazwan**. Respondents indicated a higher reliance on catering services and ready-made food, as opposed to traditional home-based preparation by skilled wazas. This shift suggests that Wazwan is gradually transforming from a cultural and ritualistic practice into a commodified service, influenced by urban lifestyles and time constraints.

Economic factors have also played a crucial role in shaping these changes. Many households reported reduced expenditure on food and social gatherings, leading to a decline in large-scale feasting. This economic rationalization has directly impacted the scale and frequency of Wazwan consumption, making it more selective and occasion-based.

Lastly, the study observes that while the form and practice of Wazwan have changed, its cultural significance remains intact. Respondents still associate Wazwan with identity, tradition, and social prestige. However, its expression has adapted to contemporary realities, reflecting a balance between cultural continuity and change.

Thus, the change is not a decline but a restructuring of tradition under modern socio-economic conditions.

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